

OPTIMIZATION OF THE CARBON-COMPOSITE WING FOR THE SKUA HIGH SPEED TARGET DRONE

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SUMMARY: This paper addresses the design optimization process of the all carbon-composite wing for the SKUA high speed target drone. The wing currently employs a conventional spar and rib construction, and the manufacturing process is by wet lay-up, vacuum bagging and oven cure. The design brief was to cut the manufacturing costs of the airframe and the wing by 35%, whilst at the same time reducing the mass of the drone.

Various construction techniques and manufacturing processes were investigated, and a two component integral wing structure manufactured in an autoclave was selected. The design optimization lead to a cost reduction of 40%, mainly achieved through the use of the two component structure as well as an improved manufacturing process. The integration and finishing time of the component was reduced by 60% and a mass saving of 10% was achieved. The wing was subjected to non destructive and structural testing for the qualification process.

KEYWORDS: SKUA high-speed target drone, main wing design optimization, tooling techniques, process development, structural qualification

INTRODUCTION

The SKUA High Speed Target drone (HTD) has been designed to simulate high speed attack aircraft during ground-to-air, air-to-air and ship-to-air combat exercises. Capable of flying at speeds of Mach 0.86 at 30 000 ft, the maximum instantaneous load factor is 7.5g, making this all composite airframe a highly loaded structure. The all-up weight of the drone is 680 kg, of which the airframe contributes to 180 kg.

Although the system has been in operation with the South African Airforce since 1992, to be able to compete in the international market, the design brief was to cut the manufacturing costs of the airframe by 35%, whilst at the same time reducing the mass of the drone.

For details of the HTD drone refer to Fig. 1.

Fig 1: SKUA High Speed Target Drone

DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

The HTD wing is swept 30° at the leading edge and uses a supercritical aerofoil section with a 10% thickness to chord ratio at the root. The wing span is 3 570 mm and provision is made for mid wing and tip stores. The design specifications include the aerodynamic load caused by a 7.5g turn, a 10g launch and recovery load and a 15g landing impact load.

As the requirement for a 7.5g sustained load could not be met with the existing propulsion unit, one of the design considerations was to reduce the airframe to such size that the payload volume and the mission flight time would not be affected. The airframe was therefore reduced to 88% of full scale, and for this reason the main wing dimensions of this technology demonstrator are 88% of full scale.

WING CONCEPT DESIGN

Conventional Wing Structure

The current wing structure employs a conventional spar and rib structure bonded to the top and bottom skins. The manufacture of the spar and rib structure is a labour intensive manual operation, the skins are manufactured by a wet lay-up, vacuum bag and oven cure process. The bond lines are difficult to control and therefore the weight control on the final structure is not optimal. The wing consists of the upper and lower skins and the internal structure. [1]

Tomahawk Wing Concept

The wing for the Tomahawk cruise missile employs an internal frame structure manufactured by a hot injection moulding process. The wing top and bottom skins are made of a thermoset pre-impregnated material. The centre structure is bonded to the top and bottom wing skins and a leading edge cap ensures good bonding along the leading edge. The wing consists of only 4 parts, namely the upper and lower skin, the leading edge cap and the internal frame structure.

Integral Spar Concept

This concept makes use of an integral spar in the wing skins. The spars are moulded into the upper and the lower skins during the manufacturing process of the skins. The material lay-up for the skins and the spars are done at the same time. The wing consists of the two wings halves, which are bonded along the centre core, and a leading edge cap which assures bonding along the front split-line.

RTM Concept

The Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process allows the whole wing to be built in one operation. The dry skin material is put into the bottom wing mould with excess material along the leading edge. The internal webs are placed into position and thermally activated foam is used to keep it in position. The excess material is placed over the internal spars and thermal foam core, while the top half of the mould is closed and sealed. The RTM process is then activated.

CONCEPT EVALUATION AND SELECTION

The Tomahawk concept showed excellent high production volume characteristics, however, the inner spar construction carries a weight penalty, due to the relative poor mechanical properties of the short fibre injection moulded materials. As the weight constraints of the SKUA airframe are critical, to achieve the desired performance specifications, this concept was not selected.

The RTM process, has its biggest advantage in the fact that it is a one component manufacturing process ideally suited to a high production volume environment. The process was however not considered due to the time limitation on the technology program, and the associated high risks of the RTM tooling development. By process of elimination, the integral spar concept was therefor the obvious choice.

Integral Spar Concept

The integral spar concept makes use of only two spars that run along the entire length of the wing. These spars form an integral part of the wing skins, providing the wing bending and torsional stiffness. The integral spars also provide the required channels in the wing to route cables and piping. Refer to Fig. 2.

Fig 2: Integral Spar Concept

DETAIL STRUCTURAL DESIGN

Load Analysis

Based on the maximum manoeuvring capability of 7.5g, the total lift load on the main wing is 43 800 N. For the design values of the bending moments and the shear force, the wing was split into 3 sections, as illustrated in Fig. 3. An elliptical load distribution along the chord centre-line was assumed with the design values for the three sections listed in Table 1. [2]

Fig 3: Wing Design and Load Analysis

Table 1: Wing Sectional Loading

SECTION	MAX SHEAR (Nm)	MAX BENDING (N)
Section 1	6 028	21 882
Section 2	4 500	12 020
Section 3	1 873	6 843

Detail Design

The conceptual design of the wing clearly highlighted the cumbersome lay-up procedures required for the integrated spar construction as presented in Fig. 2. The detail design was then adapted to an a-symmetric integral spar lay-out, whereby the spar forms part of only the lower skin. Refer to Fig. 4.

Fig 4: Optimized Integral Spar Design

The materials used in the design of the wing are listed below. The mechanical properties of these materials are not presented in this paper, as they are inherent to the products listed.

Woven Cloth:

Fibredux 920 - CX - 820 55% resin contents by weight
 T300 Carbon 2x2 twill 193 g/sqm
 Cured ply thickness 0.30 mm

Unidirectional Cloth:

Fibredux 920 - CX - TX - 133 42% resin contents by weight
 T300 Carbon 133 g/sqm
 Cured ply thickness 0.15 mm

Structural Analysis

The structural analysis was done using finite element techniques with optimization routines written for determining the optimum lamination along the wing centre-line where the

maximum shear stresses occur. The optimization process was aimed at optimizing the skin thickness and the fibre orientation in the skins. The optimization of the integral spar was driven by the manufacturing processes. The final optimization was done to ensure ease of manufacturing and minimum laminating times.

TOOLING DEVELOPMENT

Pattern

The pattern was CNC machined from a laminated block supawood. Urial or Model Lab products would have been better suited to this application due to their thermal stability for high temperature moulds. However, the supawood was selected for cost considerations. [3]

The pattern surface was prepared with a +/- 0.3 mm layer of XB5200/HY932/DY060 gelcoat, this was allowed to gel for 17 hrs at 21deg C and then coated with a 0.1 mm layer of LY5210/HY932/DY060 resin. The surface was then polished.

Moulds

The moulds were manufactured using 200 g/sqm carbon G818 in a wet lay-up process and the laminating resin was again LY5210/HY932/DY060. The mould was cured at 60° C and post-cured at 140° C. The egg-crate backing structure was then fitted to the moulds and supported by fully adjustable steel tables. The moulds were then accurately levelled with the use of a Kern ECDS theodolite system.

Tooling Jigs

The tooling required is that of the integral spar forming tool. The integral spar was machined from aluminium and bonded onto the wing skin. A carbon tool was then taken off this aluminium spar, the tool was made in the same lay-up as the wing mould. Silicon bagging was then formed to the shape of the integral spar. The integral spar tool backing is indexed with the wing mould.

MANUFACTURING PROCESS

Materials

The materials used for the skin manufacture were as specified in the detail structural analysis. To verify the tooling and the manufacturing process, and at the same time keeping the costs low, the first wing was manufactured using a thickness representative glass fibre instead of the carbon fibre. [4]

Processes

The skins were layed up according to the lay-up sequence established during the detail structural design. The spars, being part of the skin lay-up, were then formed around a silicon bladder. On completion of the skin lay-up, the tool that control the shape and height of the integral spar were fitted to the mould. The silicon bladder was then attached to the autoclave

pressure, thereby ensuring that the spar lay-up took the shape of the spar tooling. The height of the spar was directly controlled by the inner skin of the other mould. Refer to Fig. 5. The skins were then cured in the autoclave at a pressure of 7 bar and temperature of 120° C.

Fig 5: Integral Spar Tooling

Assembly

The two wing halves were prepared along the bonding surfaces. The tooling jigs assured the correct thickness of the bond lines along the leading and trailing edges and the centre spars. Araldite film adhesive was used along the bond lines. After bonding of the two wing halves the leading edge cap was bonded onto the wing.

TEST AND EVALUATION

Non Destructive Testing

The Non Destructive Testing (NDT) of the HTD wing was conducted with C-scan ultrasonic inspection. The original wing was used as a reference for the NDT tests, and subsequently cut open in sections, to allow for verification of the results. The C-scan ultra-sonic inspection provided good results, clearly indicating the uniform thickness of the bondlines along the full length of the integral spar/skin. No defects could be identified along the bondlines and the C-scan ultra-sonic inspection has been recommended as part of the wing qualification program. [5]

Structural Evaluation

The wing was structurally tested to 150 % design load. An elliptic load distribution was applied along the chord line by the use of a wiffle tree. Load/displacement measurements were conducted to verify the stiffness requirements.

Visual Evaluation

A wing was cut open in sections to verify the skin thicknesses and the bondlines. Good correlation was achieved between the C-scan ultra-sonic detection results and the bond lines thickness. No visible problem areas could be detected.

CONCLUSIONS

The design optimization lead to a cost reduction of 40%, this was mainly achieved through the use of the two component structure as well as an improved manufacturing process. The integration and finishing time of the component was reduced by 60%. A mass saving of 10% was achieved, and the mass variation on the production wing did not exceed 3%. Furthermore, the 2 component wing employs a minimum of bond lines, thereby reducing the use of the required NDT during the acceptance testing. The wings were subjected to structural qualification, by testing to the 150% of the 7.5g design load.

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